

Electronic Conduction Studies on Tantalum Oxide Films under different Metallic Counterelectrodes

K. C. KALRA* and PARVEEN KATYAL

Department of Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak-124 001

Manuscript received 4 April 1989, revised 20 June 1989, accepted 22 July 1989

DC conduction studies have been made on Ta_2O_5 anodic oxide layers with vacuum deposited Sb, Bi, Ni and Sn contacts. The effect of thickness of Ta_2O_5 on current has also been studied. Current-voltage characteristics show ohmic conduction in the lower voltage range and space charge limited conductivity for the higher voltage levels. The slopes of the space charge limited $\log I$ vs $\log V$ characteristics are found to depend on metallic counter-electrode and the values vary from 3.28 to 3.57. The gap-state density $N(E_f)$ at the Fermi level was calculated by two alternative methods and the values yielded by different methods compare well. $N(E_f)$ has been found to vary inversely with the square of the oxide thickness.

THIN anodic tantalum oxide films with thin aluminium counter-electrodes are known to produce a device which has strong rectifying properties¹⁻³. Commercial rectifying devices have been produced using tantalum oxide film in conjunction with electrolyte counter-electrode. The dc conduction in tantalum oxide thin films have received much attention in recent years. The earlier view was that charge flow was concentrated in localized defects through the dielectric^{4,5} but the recent work suggests that charge flow is distributed throughout the film^{2,6}. Young^{6,7} made charge flow studies in tantalum oxide film prepared by r.f. sputtering and preferred bulk limited conduction mechanism. Other authors suggested^{1-5,8} that charge flow is electrode limited. Gubanski and Hughes² adduced evidence for the space charge limited conduction by investigating the transport of charge through thin anodic tantalum oxide films with gold counter-electrodes. More recently, a space charge limited conduction in $Ta(-)/Ta_2O_5$ electrolyte system has been suggested⁹. It appears that the views regarding the conduction mechanism are at variance. Therefore, it was thought of interest to work with different metals to get better insight into the problem. The present work reports the dc conduction data through Ta_2O_5 films with Sb, Bi, Ni and Sn as counterelectrodes. Conduction studies through tantalum oxide films of different thicknesses have also been made.

Experimental

Tantalum specimens (2×10^{-4} m² area) with short tags were cut from sheets of purity 99.9% Ta. The samples were polished mechanically and chemically by the usual methods. Anodisation on Ta at a constant current density (50 A m⁻²) in 100 mol m⁻³ aqueous citric acid was carried out using an electronically operated constant current

generator for 28, 57 and 85 s and the films formed were upto the formation voltage of 50, 100 and 150 V respectively. The thicknesses of the films were determined using Faraday's law and were found to be 81, 165 and 245 nm ($\pm 0.5\%$) respectively. Encapsulation technique was employed for the electrical conduction study. The sample was mounted on a perspex piece with a suitable depression and the contact with bulk tantalum was obtained with a standard thermosetting silver preparation. Edges of the specimens were protected by epoxy resin to prevent conduction through edges. The contact with anodic film was made by evaporating Sb, Bi, Ni and Sn metals separately in vacuum at $2-3 \times 10^{-5}$ mm/Hg pressure using a Hind Hivac 12A 4' coating unit. The conduction studies were made with a dc microvoltmeter and a standard resistance of 192 k Ω in series with the specimen. Citric acid used was of A.R. grade. The density and dielectric constant of Ta_2O_5 film were taken as 7930 kg m⁻³ and 27.6 respectively as reported¹⁰. All data refer to 298 K.

Results and Discussion

Current and voltage were measured across tantalum oxide film (81 nm thick) using bulk Ta as positive electrode and Sb, Bi, Ni and Sn metals separately as negative counter-electrodes. In general, $\log I$ vs $\log V$ (Fig. 1) curves show a gradual transition from a slowly rising region to a steeply rising region. The slowly rising curves represent the ohmic conduction region where I is proportional to V and the steeply rising curves represent the space-charge limited current (SCLC) region where I is proportional to V^n . The values of n for Sb, Bi, Ni and Sn counter-electrodes were found to be 3.28, 3.54, 3.57 and 3.50 respectively. Similar gradual transitions in $\log I$ vs $\log V$ curves (Fig. 2) are also reported for three Ta_2O_5 samples of thicknesses

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log I$ vs $\log V$ for different counter-electrodes : (○) Sb, (▲) Bi, (●) Ni and (△) Sn.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log I$ vs $\log V$ for different thicknesses of Ta_2O_5 films : (○) 81, (▲) 165 and (△) 245 nm.

Fig. 3. $I-V$ characteristics plotted as $\log (I/V)$ vs $V^{1/2}$ for different counter-electrodes : (○) Sb, (▲) Bi, (●) Ni and (△) Sn.

Fig. 4. $I-V$ characteristics plotted as $\log (I/V)$ vs $V^{1/2}$ for different thicknesses of Ta_2O_5 films : (○) 81, (▲) 165 and (△) 245 nm.

81, 165 and 245 nm. The plots of $\log I/V$ vs $V^{1/2}$ for different counter-electrodes and at different thicknesses of Ta_2O_5 are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 and they are non-linear. This non-linear relationship indicates the absence of Poole-Frenkel effect and does reinforce our opinion that trap limited

SCLC mechanism is operating in Ta-Ta₂O₅-metal system.

Anodic tantalum oxide films have been reported to be amorphous⁹⁻¹¹. Recently Micocci *et al.*¹² calculated directly the density of states in the gap of amorphous films from SCLC measurements using an analytical method. According to this method, the equation for the density of states $N(E_F)$ is given by equation (1),

$$N(E_F) = \frac{\epsilon\epsilon_0 V}{qkTd^2} \left(\frac{(2\alpha-3)\beta+\gamma}{(2-\alpha)(1-\alpha)+\beta} + \alpha \right) (2-\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the film, ϵ_0 the permittivity of vacuum, q the electronic charge, d the thickness of the oxide film, k the Boltzmann constant and α , β and γ are,

$$\alpha = \frac{d(\log V)}{d(\log I)}, \beta = \frac{d^2(\log V)}{d(\log I)^2} \text{ and } \gamma = \frac{d^3(\log V)}{d(\log I)^3}$$

In deriving equation (1) it was assumed that only majority carriers (holes) were injected by a perfect ohmic contact and the distribution of imperfections and the mobility of the free carriers were spatially uniform and independent of electric field. Further, quasiequilibrium conditions were reached at any injection rate, and the occupancy of space was determined by the position of quasi-Fermi level E_F . The density of free majority carriers was described by Boltzmann statistics. It was also assumed that the electrical length of the samples was independent of applied voltage and current and there was a negligible diffusion current.

Equation (1) gives a method of evaluating $N(E_F)$ directly from a log-log plot of the $I-V$. In our case, $\log I$ vs $\log V$ plots were found to be linear, therefore, β and γ can be taken as zero and the equation (1) becomes

$$N(E_F) = \frac{\epsilon\epsilon_0 V}{qkTd^2} \alpha(2-\alpha) \quad (2)$$

We employed equation (2) to calculate the density of gap state $N(E_F)$ in Ta-Ta₂O₅-metal system. The values of α were the slopes of SCLC region of $\log I$ vs $\log V$ plots and V was taken equal to the well-defined transition voltage V_t . The calculated values of $N(E_F)$ for different metallic counter-electrode and different thickness of the Ta₂O₅ films are given in Table 1.

The gap-state distribution in SCLC measurements may be described with a good approximation by a

TABLE 1—DENSITY OF STATES $N(E)$ CALCULATED USING EQUATIONS (2) AND (3) FOR DIFFERENT Ta-Ta₂O₅-METAL SYSTEMS

Counter electrode	Thickness nm	$N(E)$ ($10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ eV}^{-1}$)	
		Eqn. (2)	Eqn. (3)
Sb	81	9.6	10.7
Sb	165	2.5	2.7
Sb	245	1.1	1.3
Bi	81	8.7	8.6
Ni	81	9.6	11.7
Sn	81	8.9	9.0

model with constant density of traps around the Fermi level. The current is given by the relation¹³,

$$I \propto V \exp(V/V_0) \quad (3)$$

where,

$$V_0 = \frac{qkTd^2}{\epsilon\epsilon_0} N(E_F)$$

$N(E_F)$ calculated from equations (2) and (3) (Table 1) agree well. The density of the states depends both on the nature of the counter-electrodes and on the thicknesses of the oxide film. The value of $N(E_F)$ varies almost inversely with the square of the thickness.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.K.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship. Thanks are also due to the Head of the Chemistry Department for facilities.

References

1. F. O. ARIS and T. J. LEWIS, *J. Phys. (D)*, 1978, 6, 1067.
2. S. M. GUBANSKI and D. M. HUGHES, *Thin Solid Films*, 1978, 52, 119.
3. M. W. JONES and D. M. HUGHES, *J. Phys. (D)*, 1974, 7, 119.
4. N. SCHWARTZ and N. N. AXELROD, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1969, 116, 460.
5. D. A. VERMILYBA, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1963, 110, 250.
6. P. L. YOUNG, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1976, 47, 235.
7. P. L. YOUNG, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1975, 46, 2794.
8. S. IKONOFISOV and N. ELSENKOV, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1978, 86, 105.
9. M. MERIKOS-HUKOVIC and M. ORRAJ-ORRIC, *Thin Solid Films*, 1986, 145, 39.
10. L. YOUNG, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1959, 244, 41.
11. L. YOUNG, "Anodic Oxide Films", Academic, New York, 1961.
12. G. MICOCCHI, P. SICILIANO and A. TEPORÉ, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1988, 64, 1885.
13. M. A. LAMPERT and P. MARK, "Current Injection in Solids", Academic, New York, 1970.